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FORMATION OF NON-VERBAL VOCABULARY

Annotation

This article considers the formation of non-verbal vocabulary of the language. Here the features of non-verbal means of communication are revealed. Also acquainted with the basics of non-verbal communication, considered the features of non-verbal communication and studied the functions of non-verbal communication.

Key words: Non-verbal vocabulary of the language, means of communication, features of communication, functions, facial expressions, gestures, eye contact and intonation.

СТАНОВЛЕНИЕ НЕВЕРБАЛЬНОЙ ЛЕКСИКИ

Аннотация

В данной статье рассмотрено становление невербальной лексики языка. Здесь выявлено особенности невербальных средств общения. А также ознакомлено с основами невербального общения, рассмотрено особенности невербального общения и изучено функции невербального общения.

Ключевые слова: Невербальной лексики языка, средств общения, особенности общения, функции, мимика, жесты, зрительный контакт, интонация.

НОВЕРБАЛ СЎЗЛАРИНИНГ ШАКЛЛАНИШИ

Аннотация

Ушбу мақолада тилнинг новербал луғатини шакллантириш борасида фикр юритилган. Шунингдек новербал алоқа воситаларининг хусусиятлари очиб берилди. Бундан ташқари, новербал мулоқот асослари билан танишилиб, унинг хусусиятлари ва вазифалари кўриб чиқилган.

Калит сўзлар: Тилнинг новербал луғати, алоқа воситалари, алоқа хусусиятлари, функциялари, юз ифодалари, имо-ишоралар, кўз билан алоқа, интонация.

Introduction. Body language is recognized as the most widely spoken language in the world. This recognition gives many of us the right to think that non-verbal means of communication - facial expressions, gestures, eye contact, and intonation - are universal, regardless of where we are and with whom we communicate. However, the culture of each country develops according to its own laws, and each country has its own characteristics of non-verbal communication.

Knowing these features will help everyone to effectively build communication with the interlocutor in "foreign territory" and, of course, feel much more confident during this communication.

The main features are observed among the symbolic gestures. As a rule, these are gestures of greeting and farewell, consent and denial, approval and censure, calls for silence, etc. The implementation of eye contact, tactile forms of expression of relationships, spatial arrangement during communication also have distinctive features. Let us dwell on this in more detail.

Literature review. According to the method of communication, verbal (verbal) and non-verbal (non-verbal) communication are distinguished. In my essay, I will consider non-verbal communication.

"Every movement of the soul has its natural expression in voice, gesture, facial expressions," wrote Cicero. The language of gestures, facial expressions, body movements is called the language of speech communication.

The method of organizing non-verbal means of communication learned by a person and transformed into an individual, concretely sensual form of actions and deeds is called non-verbal behavior.

Non-verbal means can be reduced to kinetic (body movements), spatial (organization of behavior, interpersonal communication), and temporal characteristics of interaction.

Non-verbal means perform informative and regulatory functions in the process of communication.

Many scientists say that the verbal channel is used to convey information, and the non-verbal channel is used to "discuss" interpersonal relationships.

Regardless of the cultural level of a person, words and the movements accompanying them coincide with such a degree of predictability that some scientists argue that a well-trained person can determine by his voice what movement his interlocutor makes at the moment of pronouncing a particular phrase.

Therefore, in order to understand the meaning of the statement, it is not enough to penetrate the meaning of the words, it is necessary to understand the feelings of the speaker, to analyze his non-verbal behavior.

Psychological research shows that emotions not only depend on the situation of communication, but also have a significant impact on its deployment, on the manifestation of the emotional appearance of each of the participants.

A feature of body language is that its manifestation is due to the impulses of our subconscious. The impossibility of forging such impulses allows us to trust this language more than the usual, verbal communication channel.

"The area of feelings – the emotional sphere," writes P.V. Simonov, "is not amenable to direct control. Emotions, like other human mental processes, are regulated by the centers of the brain, are expressed in a variety of motor acts - gestures, facial expressions, expressive body movements, changes in voice and speech.

Research Methodology. One can start with the fact that the non-verbal components of communication are part of the orienting basis of communication for the communicator (speaker). In other words, the nature of communication from the very beginning is partially determined by spatial and some other visual "keys", and in this link it is completely unimportant what place the non-verbal components will occupy in the communication process itself.

However, the non-verbal components of communication can also be considered from the point of view of the recipient as part of the orienting basis for his communicative activity. From this point of view, non-verbal "keys" may be common for the communicator and the recipient, and may be significant only for the latter; this is a part of such "keys", which, from the point of view of the communicator, enters the executive phase of his communicative activity. Here arises the main problem for modern studies of non-verbal communication, the problem of the relationship between non-verbal behavior and non-verbal communication as such, i.e. non-intentional and international components of the communicator's communicative activity. Non-verbal components of communication can also act as part of the executive phase of communication, not being significant for the communication process as a whole and only supplementing, clarifying, changing the understanding of the message by the recipient.

Finally, they can be insignificant for the recipient, being a kind of cost of proper communicative behavior.

Analysis and results

Here we analyzed some of the types of nonverbal communication.

Gestures of consent and denial. During communication, people of different nationalities and cultures nod their heads. The nod can be safely attributed to the most common feature of non-verbal communication in different countries.

We are accustomed to the fact that a simple nod of the head means "Yes" or an affirmation. But in Turkey, Greece, Bulgaria and India, the nod has the opposite meaning. In order to express agreement with what you are saying, a Turk, a Greek, a Bulgarian, and an Indian will shake their heads slightly from side to side, which in our non-verbal language is associated with a negative answer.

Quick head nods in Japanese indicate that the person is listening to you very carefully. But this does not mean that he agrees with what you say.

Gestures that can puzzle a foreigner also exist among the Arabs. They express their disagreement with something with a short but sharp movement of the head back. All this is accompanied by a resounding clatter.

Perhaps many of you are familiar with how people in the Middle East express their indignation. They impulsively and sharply raise their arms bent at the elbows on both sides of the face. Annoyance from what is happening is expressed with the help of rotational movements of the hands of both hands. The Arabs demonstrate the refusal or liberation from an unpleasant deed by a kind of cleansing of the palms one against the other, while the arms are bent at the elbows.

Gestures of approval. Gestures are not only movements of the hands, they are movements of the head, legs and, in general, the whole torso. It is generally accepted that gestures have a social origin, and therefore the features of non-verbal communication in different countries are especially pronounced. Directly this applies to gestures of approval.

How do we express our approval in public places - at concerts, meetings, rallies, etc.? Most of the time we just applaud. Ovarions can be long and friendly, but they can be short and calm. Ultimately, it all depends on the type of event and how satisfied we are with the event.

How do Americans show their approval? Few of them applaud like we do. In most cases, they pound their fists and feet on a hard surface. Also in Germany. Knocking fists on the table is one of the forms of showing approval and gratitude to the speaker.

The Arabs, satisfied with the successful phrase of the speaker, will surely clap their outstretched fingers on the palm of the interlocutor. So they express satisfaction and approval of what is happening.

Approving their actions, the British and Spaniards slap their foreheads with their palms. Therefore, they show that they are very pleased with themselves.

A Frenchman will express his admiration for something very simply and gracefully. He will connect the tips of three fingers, bring them to his lips, and then, raising his chin high, will send a gentle kiss into the air.

Right and left hand use. In the culture of non-verbal communication in many countries, gestures of insincerity are usually associated with gestures with the left hand. It is believed that the right hand is "cultivated" and does what it needs to. But the left hand does what it wants, and its gestures betray the hidden feelings of the owner.

In our country, it is not customary to attach special importance to the right or left hand. The exception is a handshake with the right hand. But for those who profess Islam, the left hand is considered unclean and serves only for hygienic purposes. Giving a Muslim money or any object with your left hand, you yourself, unwittingly, can insult the person.

In Uzbekistan, as well as in many European countries, in order to discover and identify yourself in a large group, it is customary to raise your hand up and make a slight nod of your head.

We all studied or are studying in schools, technical schools, institutes, and we know perfectly well how a student or a student who is ready for an answer manifests himself. In addition, if for us it is a raised hand with an open palm, then in most European schools it is a raised hand with the index finger pointing upwards.

If a European speaks about himself, he points to his chest with his hand. But the Chinese and Japanese in a conversation about themselves will definitely show their noses.

Sight. One of the most informative means of non-verbal communication is the look and expression of the eyes. Unfortunately, our compatriots are in many ways inferior to the Americans in terms of the power of their gaze.

The habit of looking "eye to eye", which is characteristic of many representatives of Western countries, is not perceived positively by everyone. And the peculiarity of many Americans to look "point-blank" into the eyes of the interlocutor is even considered rude.

For most Eastern cultures, avoiding eye contact is considered respectful. There is even a widespread belief among the Chinese that only enemies look straight in the eyes. Therefore, staring is regarded as an insult.

Mimic. Describing the features of non-verbal communication in different countries, it is important to note that all over the world, perhaps, only facial expressions are perceived by everyone in the same way. Happy people smile, unlucky people frown, and so on.

One of the brightest manifestations of facial expressions is a smile. Speaking of national characteristics, let's compare the smile of Russians and Americans.

In American communication, a smile is primarily a signal of politeness. It is obligatory not only when greeting, but also in the course of all communication.

Our people call a constant polite smile "on duty" and consider it a manifestation of insincerity and secrecy.

It is not customary for us to smile at strangers and automatically respond to a smile with a smile. In most cases, if a stranger smiled at us, then we involuntarily ask ourselves the question: "Do we really know each other?"

If an American accidentally meets someone's gaze, he will definitely smile at this person. What will we do? We'll just look away.

Acoustic non-verbal means. Acoustic non-verbal means of communication include crying, laughter, snoring, sighing, gnashing of teeth, and so on.

We are used to the fact that laughter means joy, and crying means pain and sadness. But in some African countries, laughter is not a manifestation of fun at all, but an indicator of amazement and confusion.

It is natural for most Americans to blow their nose loudly, chew defiantly, cough loudly, and so on in public places. We do not approve of the direct and open expression of natural manifestations.

Conclusion/Recommendations. Psychologists have found that in the process of human interaction, from 60 to 80% of communication is carried out through non-verbal

means of expression, and only 20-40% of information is transmitted using verbal ones.

These data make us think about the meaning of "non-verbal" for the psychology of communication and mutual understanding of people, pay special attention to the meaning of human gestures and facial expressions, and also give rise to a desire to master the art of interpreting this special language - body language, which we all speak without even realizing this.

Although communication through body language has been practiced for over a million years, the scientific study of this phenomenon has only begun in recent years, and it gained particular popularity in the 1970s. In addition, it can be foreseen that by the end of our century, people all over the world will learn about this phenomenon and that body language and its significance for communication will be specially taught in educational institutions.

In fact, the surrounding reality and the people living in it are the best scientific and testing ground. Consciously observing your own and other people's gestures is the best way to explore the communication techniques used by the most complex and interesting biological organism - man himself.

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